

INFLUENCE OF DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES ON SELF - EFFICACY OF TEACHER - TRAINEES

Amola Kumari
Prof. Pravat Kumar Dhal

Abstract

Education is an instrument for bringing out the potentialities of human beings and effectiveness of a system of education and is mainly dependent upon its teachers. In all education system, the teacher is the enabler, the inspiration and also the constraint. Teaching is an art and the quality of teaching depends on love, dedication and devotion of the teacher towards the subject of the knowledge. Self-efficacy plays a major part in determining our chances for success; in fact some psychologists rate self-efficacy above talent in the recipe for success. We need to pay special attention to self-efficacy when setting goals to make sure that our efficacy beliefs are in line with our aims and not working against them.

The purpose of the study is to study self efficacy among the teacher trainees with respect to their gender, educational qualification, medium of instruction and locale. The method adopted for the study was survey method. The population of the study comprised of all the teacher trainees who were pursuing B.Ed. in different Colleges of Education in Patna. One hundred samples were selected randomly from four different Colleges of Education of Patna. Teachers Efficacy Scale (TES) developed by Dr. T. Pradeep Kumar (2011) was used for data collection. Data was analysed with the help of suitable statistical techniques. It was found that there is a significant difference in mean scores of male and female, under graduate and post graduate, rural and urban teacher trainees in self-efficacy while there is no significant difference in mean scores of English medium and Hindi medium teacher trainees in their self-efficacy.

Key words: Teacher trainees, B.Ed. and Self-efficacy

Education is an instrument for bringing out the potentialities of human beings and effectiveness of a system of education and is mainly dependent upon its teachers. In all education system, the teacher is the enabler, the inspiration and also the constraint. Teaching is an art and the quality of teaching depends on the love,

dedication and devotion of the teacher towards the subject of the knowledge. Self-efficacy, or confidence as it is commonly known, is one of the most enabling psychology models to have been adopted into positive psychology. It is the optimistic self-belief in our competence or chances of successfully accomplishing a task and producing a favourable outcome.

Self-efficacy is certainly worth having because as Henry Ford has put it, 'whether you believe you can or you can't, you are right'. And Gandhi perfectly understood the pivotal role that self-belief plays in our lives. Self-efficacy plays a major part in determining our chances for success; in fact some psychologists rate self-efficacy above talent in the recipe for success. We need to pay special attention to self-efficacy when setting goals to make sure that our efficacy beliefs are in line with our aims and not working against them. So where does self-efficacy come from and how can you get more of it? The originator of the theory, Albert Bandura names four sources of efficacy beliefs.

Bandura has identified four factors affecting self-efficacy:

- i) **Experience, or "enactive attainment"**: The experience of mastery is the most important factor determining a person's self-efficacy. Success raises self-efficacy, while failure lowers it.
- ii) **Modeling, or "vicarious experience"**: Modeling is experienced as, "If they can do it, I can do it as well". When we see someone succeeding, our own self-efficacy increases; where we see people failing, our self-efficacy decreases.
- iii) **Social persuasion**: Social persuasion generally manifests as direct encouragement or discouragement from another person. Discouragement is generally more effective at decreasing a person's self-efficacy than encouragement is at increasing it.

- iv) **Physiological factors:** In stressful situations, people commonly exhibit signs of distress: shakes, aches and pains, fatigue, fear, nausea, etc. Perceptions of these responses in one can markedly alter self-efficacy.

There are three dimensions in self-efficacy, namely:

- 1) Level or magnitude: belief in his/her own ability that is able to do task/ work at various different levels of difficulty.
- 2) Strength: belief that someone has that he has the ability and endurance in doing a task.
- 3) Generality: Person's belief in his/her own ability to be able to do task/work in various conditions (Noyelles, Hornik & Johnson, 2014).

High self-efficacy can affect motivation in both positive and negative ways. In general, people with high self-efficacy are more likely to make efforts to complete a task, and to persist longer in those efforts, than those with low self-efficacy.

A negative effect of low self-efficacy is that it can lead to a state of learned helplessness.

Significance of the study

In the present scenario teachers aspire to be seen as true professionals with competency, knowledge concerning the content, skill of teaching and methods of instruction. Teachers' ideas, understandings, self-efficacy and attitudes influence their quality of instruction. Therefore, these features must be considered in the teacher education programs. Teacher training of prospective teachers has very important role to develop the qualified teachers. Quality of teacher training enhance teacher's self-efficacy. Teachers' self-efficacy has been found to be predictive of attitudes towards teaching profession. In the same way, attitudes towards teaching profession also influence the way students learn. For this reason, it is

extremely useful for pre-service teachers who are the creator of the next generations of learners, to have high self-efficacy beliefs so that they become competence and to give them the opportunity to show their competence and perform the profession in the best way possible. That's why researcher wants to study the influence of certain demographic variables on Self - Efficacy of prospective teachers.

Operational Definitions:

Self-efficacy - Teacher trainees beliefs in his/her own ability to organize and succeed in teaching.

Teacher-trainees - A teacher trainee is a student- teacher enrolled for the professional degree of Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) in session 2018-2020.

Objectives

- i. To find out the significant difference in self-efficacy of teacher trainees on the basis of gender, educational qualification, medium of instruction and locality.

Null Hypotheses

- i. There is no significant difference between mean scores of male and female teacher trainees in their self-efficacy.
- ii. There is no significant difference between mean scores of under graduate and post graduate teacher trainees in self-efficacy.
- iii. There is no significant difference in mean scores of self-efficacy among teacher trainees on the basis of their medium of instruction.
- iv. There is no significant difference between mean scores of urban and rural teacher trainees in their self-efficacy.

Method adopted for the study

Considering the nature of the problem, the method used for the present study is survey method.

Population

The population of the study comprised of all the teacher-trainees who were pursuing B.Ed. course in different Colleges of Education in Patna.

Sample

100 samples were selected randomly from 4 different B.Ed. Colleges of Patna.

Tool

The following tool was used for data collection:

Teachers Efficacy Scale (TES) developed by Dr. T. Pradeep Kumar (2011)

Statistical techniques used

Mean, S.D. and t-test were used for data analysis.

Results and Discussion

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between mean scores of male and female teacher trainees in self-efficacy.

TABLE 1
Mean, SD and t-ratio based on gender

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio	Remarks
Male	63	67.48	4.80	5.84	S*
Female	37	73.53	5.12		

(S* means significant)

It is inferred from table 1 that the t-value is 5.84 which is more than the table value 2.626 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It means there is significant difference in mean scores of male and female teacher trainees in self-efficacy. From table 1, it can be inferred that the self efficacy of female teacher trainees is better than the self efficacy of male teacher trainees.

Hypothesis 2- There is no significant difference between mean scores of under graduate and post graduate teacher trainees in self-efficacy.

TABLE 2
Mean, SD and t-ratio based on educational qualification

Educational Qualification	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio	Remarks
Under Graduate	71	75.48	7.43	3.57	S*
Post Graduate	29	68.94	8.62		

(S* means significant)

It is inferred from the table 2 that the t-value is 3.57 which is more than the table value 2.626 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It means there is significant difference in mean scores of under graduate and post graduate teacher trainees in

self-efficacy. So, from table 2 it can be inferred that the self efficacy of under graduate teacher trainees is better than the self efficacy of post graduate teacher trainees.

Hypothesis 3- There is no significant difference in mean scores of self-efficacy among teacher trainees on the basis of their medium of instruction.

TABLE 3
Mean, SD and t-ratio based on medium of instruction

Medium of instruction	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio	Remarks
Hindi	61	70.56	6.43	0.69	NS*
English	39	71.48	6.52		

(NS* means not significant)

It is inferred from the table 3 that the t-value is 0.69 which is less than the table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It means there is no significant difference in mean scores of Hindi medium and English medium teacher trainees in self-efficacy.

Hypothesis 4- There is no significant difference between mean scores of urban and rural teacher trainees in self-efficacy.

TABLE 4
Mean, SD and t-ratio based on habitation

Habitation	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio	Remarks
Rural	42	66.35	5.43	2.81	S*
Urban	58	69.63	6.21		

(S* means significant)

It is inferred from the table 4 that the t-value is 2.81 which is more than the table value 2.626 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It means there is significant difference in mean scores of rural and urban teacher trainees in self-efficacy. From table 4, it can be inferred that the self efficacy of urban teacher trainees is better than the self efficacy of rural teacher trainees.

Conclusion

On the basis of present study it may be concluded that there is a significant difference in mean scores of male and female, under graduate and post graduate, rural and urban teacher trainees in self-efficacy while there is a no significant difference in mean scores of English medium and Hindi medium teacher trainees in self-efficacy. These findings will help the School management, educational planners and Government in different ways for upliftment of society.

References

- Adams, P., & O'Neill, J. (2010). Heeding parents in educational reform. *New Zealand Journal of Teachers' Work*, 7(1), 1-2.
- Aggarwal, J.C. (2004). *Development of Education System in India*. Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
- Aggarwal, J.C. (2007). *Educational Policy in India: 1992 and Review 2000 and 2005*. Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
- Ak it, N. (2007). Educational reform in Turkey. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 27 (2), 129-137.
- Anyon, J. (1995). Race, social class, and educational reform in an inner city school. *Teachers College Record*, 97, 69-94.
- Asif, F. (2013). Prospective teachers' beliefs about concepts of teaching and learning. *International Journal of Academic Research and Reflection*, 1 (1), 41-51.

- Azizi, N. (2012). Educational Policy Makers' Views on Secondary Education Relevance to the World of Work in Iran: A Critical Reflection on 1990s Educational Reform. *International Journal of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research* 1 (8), August 2012, ISSN 2277 3630 on 2.4.19 .
- Bocchio, M. C., Grinberg ,S., & Villagran, C. (2016) Reception and enactment of the compulsory secondary education reform. Stephen Ball's contributions to the study of educational policies in schools of Santa Cruz province, Argentina. *Archivos Analíticos de Políticas Educativas*, 24(9).
- Brinkmann, S. (2018). Teachers' beliefs and educational reform in India: from 'learner-centred' to 'learning-centred' education. *Comparative Education*. 1-21. 10.1080/03050068.2018.1541661
- British Council English in Education. Bihar Profile. Retrieved from https://www.britishcouncil.org/sites/default/files/bihar_education_summary_report.
- Burrola, M., Vera J. (2013) Study about ICT skills in Junior High School Teachers under Mexico's educational reform. *International Journal of Psychological Research*. 6 (2): 59-70
- Carol,W., Sachiko, J., Kacey, J., & Richard, L. (2014). Making Math Count: Tribal College Leadership in Education Reform on the Northern Cheyenne Reservation. *American Indian Culture and Research Journal*: 2014, 3(3), pp. 107-134.
- Chauhan, S. S. (2010). *Advanced Educational Psychology*. 7th edition. Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- Chiangkul, W. (1998). *The Crisis and Chance for Education Reform and Thai Society*. Office of the National Education Commission, Bangkok.

